

Researchers and Supporters: Supply and Demand

Post Conference Report on the Session Findings

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Introduction

The session was a birds of a feather group discussion at the SURF Research Day 2025 in Gooiland, Hilversum, the Netherlands. The session was presented to the participants in three parts, an introduction, separate group discussions, and a discussion to match the work done between the separate group discussions.

The introduction covered why we held the session; we as research supporters want to enumerate needs of researchers about managing research data and / or code as well as the support services offered by supporters, and to match the services to the needs. We also set ourselves sub-goals including identifying where there are unmet needs, unused services, and also attempting to find situations where there may be a language usage mismatch. The example presented to the group for the language mismatch was about the term database, as a researcher a database might be understood as a tool that includes database software, a content management system, and search software for people to explore data entries, whereas for (ICT) supporters when they hear database they will think of a specific software such as PostgreSQL or MongoDB.

The apart and together discussions were held in the context of the phases of the project lifecycle: Planning, Collection, Analysis, Publication/Archiving, Training, and Other. For researchers, we collected their needs in person and online with forms asking for their needs, their stage on the academic ladder, and the main category of their scientific researcher (Natural and Environmental Sciences, Social Sciences, Engineering, and Health and Medicine). For supporters we asked in person and online for their services, where they provide support (in a faculty, for a whole university, or nationwide), and the category for the type of support they provide (ICT, Data Management, Privacy, Software Engineering, Grant Writing, Publishing Support, Project Management, or Other).

Before the session, the pre-session submissions were categorized and hung on posters with the phases of the project lifecycle. Due to the nature of the event, it was expected ahead of time that the supporters would need to be broken up into two groups, so the pre-event submissions for supporters were duplicated so each group would have the same starting point.

During the session, the apart discussions broke the participants into three groups, one group of researchers and two groups of supporters. As we expected beforehand, far more supporters than researchers attended this session, with fewer than 10 people in the researchers group. Each of the three groups had one or more discussion leaders. The goal of these discussions was to solicit from the participants more responses on needs and services, to discuss how the groups work on a project, and to try to identify more possibilities.

The together discussion brought everyone in the room back together, using the researcher needs as the main goal, and matching the supporter services with the researcher needs. The submissions were physically moved from the apart discussion posters to the final together posters.

Results

The full listing of the researcher needs and the supporter services can be found in the spreadsheet (available in XLSX and ODS formats) in the data archive.

Pre-conference, we received 1 researcher need, and 8 supporter services through the online form. The total number of researcher needs at the end of the session was 15, and supporter services were 50.

While we did not keep a record of the number of attendees, we can say that each supporter group in the apart discussions had at least 15 participants, and the researcher group had fewer than 10 participants.

Table 1 below shows the results of the matching portion of the session, and includes all the collected researcher needs:

Phase	Researcher Need	Matching Support Service
Planning	Help writing a proposal to access HPC (Snellius)	Infrastructure Support
		HPC Guidance "Which Infrastructure"
		HPC Training (Cluster, Cloud)
Planning	Efficient workflow to manage data	Data infrastructure development advice
		DMP Review
Planning	Which metadata standard works for my data -> and what do I do with it?	Data Management Support
		Advice on Research Methods
		RDM Advice
		Methodology Support
Collection	To store collected data in the field	Developing tools to collect data

Collection	To store confidential data collected in the field	Developing tools to collect data
Collection	Digital data collection (Engineering templates)	Data infrastructure development advice
		Developing tools to collect data
Collection	Pipeline for metadata creation as data is created	RDM advice
Collection	Transcription tools -> which ones are ok for sensitive data?	General questions on privacy and information security
Collection	Easier tools for metadata creation	
Collection	Access/Guidance HPC	
Analysis	Text mining & analysis of (qualitative) documents	HPC Consultance and Support
		Advice on code writing
		Programming Workshops
		Research software development
Publishing/Archiving	Support with Graphics Design	Bridge researchers to other support service
Publishing/Archiving	Someone to review my publication	
Publishing/Archiving	Infrastructure to store & publish confidential data and manage access	
Training	More courses on programming languages (advances)	Programming Workshops
Training	Metadata templates	

Discussion

During the apart discussions in the researcher group, the discussion leaders noted that several members self-reported they were actually supporters but acting on behalf of researchers. The discussion leaders did not ask these people to move to the supporter groups, therefore some of the researcher needs can also be seen as the needs of researchers as seen through the lens of supporters.

While most of the researcher needs had matching supporter services, there were 5 that did not have matching services. Viewing the unmatched needs however, the authors do have a few notes:

- Easier tools for metadata creation - could be met with research software development
- Access/Guidance HPC – could be met with the HPC consultancy and support
- Someone to review my publications – publication support services do exist at many universities, however we believe we did not receive any service specifications from publishing supporters.
- Infrastructure to store and publish confidential data and manage access – We know that SURF, DANS, and UMCs are working on making this more of a robust system. Most universities also have storage solutions for storing confidential data, however not always an easy-to-use publishing solution.
- Metadata templates – For this one the author believes this is more of a mismatch, because metadata was written, however perhaps documentation was intended. Metadata should always have a standardized computer-readable metadata template, whereas documentation is more free-format and should include the relevant human-readable information for a dataset. Assuming documentation, the authors offer README templates for code and data publications and know that many other universities offer similar templates. If it is indeed metadata, perhaps the researchers have the need for more tools to be able to record metadata in collection and analysis.

Conclusions

Our goals going into the session were to match support services to researcher needs, to find unmet needs, identify services with no-demand, and to try to identify language gaps between researchers and supporters. As far as these goals go, we were only able to successfully match the researcher needs on hand to the support services within the room. Due to the participation levels and imbalances therein, we cannot draw conclusions for the other three goals.

Future Steps

This session should be held again in the future to collect more responses from researchers and supporters alike, and to balance out the supporter biases coming to national events like the SURF Research Day, it should be held at primarily research-oriented events.

We have included the materials to run this session yourselves in the repository that accompanies this report. This includes PDFs for the submission sheets and the posters to hang and organize the submissions on. These PDFs were made with Adobe InDesign, and the InDesign files have also been included. The PDFs all use the ISO A paper format standard, thus they can be scaled to different page sizes as needed.

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